

IMPACT FORCE IDENTIFICATION FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING A NON-NEGATIVE BAYESIAN REGULARIZATION ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new approach of impact force identification for composite structures with consideration of the non-negative property of the time history of impact force. A Rayleigh-Ritz type method is employed to establish a state-space model to describe the forward dynamics of a composite structure under impact. Then the impact force identification problem is formulated as a linear least square regularization problem with the impact force vector as the unknown. A newly developed inverse analysis method with Bayesian regularization is employed to solve the ill-posed impact force identification problem, while non-negative constraints are applied in the regularization term. The newly proposed impact force identification approach is illustrated by numerical examples, and results have demonstrated the effectiveness of the approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

In aerospace engineering, one major concern in the design of composite structure is the invisible damages caused by low-velocity impact, which are difficult to detect and may significantly affect the integrity of the structure. Therefore, one important task of an efficient and reliable structural health monitoring (SHM) system for composite structures is to detect and identify the impact force whenever an impact event occurs [1].

During the past two decades, many model-based impact force identification methods have been developed [2-5], including inverse analysis based on deconvolution [6,7]. Usually, the deconvolution methods are considered as “straightforward”, which employ impulse responses (or called Green functions) to identify the impact force time history. However, the deconvolution-based impact force identification is typically a well-known ill-posed inverse problem which is vulnerable to noise and whose solution may be unstable if there exists. In this case, regularization is usually required so as to obtain a stable bounded solution. The most widely used regularization in inverse impact force analyses is the Tikhonov regularization which relaxes the ill-conditioning by balancing the original objective function and a smoothness condition on the solution. The major difficulty of applying the Tikhonov regularization lies in how to efficiently find the optimal regularization parameter. To overcome the deficiencies of the traditional Tikhonov regularization, recently Bayesian regularization (also known as augmented Tikhonov regularization) which can adaptively determine the regularization parameter and detect the noise level in a data-driven manner, has been successfully employed for traffic force and impact force identification [8-10], demonstrating the potential of Bayesian regularization in solving ill-posed inverse problems in SHM. However, the Bayesian regularization is still within the framework of traditional Tikhonov regularization, and the identified impact force has fluctuations as well as many negative components which is conflict with the non-negative property of impact force.

The aim of this paper is to present a non-negative Bayesian regularization approach to identify the impact force time history for composite structures. After a Rayleigh-Ritz type method is employed to establish a state-space model for a composite structure under impact, the impact force identification problem is formulated as a linear least square regularization problem. An inverse analysis method with Bayesian regularization with non-negative constraints is employed to solve the ill-posed impact force identification problem. Numerical studies are performed to validate the proposed impact force identification approach.

2 STATE-SPACE MODEL FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

A rectangular composite plate with a symmetric layup is considered in this study. Based on the classical laminate theory, the governing equation for the composite plate under impact can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(t)d(x - x_{impact}, y - y_{impact}) = & rh \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} D_{11} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + 2D_{16} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \\
 & + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + 2D_{26} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \\
 & + 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} D_{16} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + D_{26} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + 2D_{66} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $f(t)$ is the impact force, (x_{impact}, y_{impact}) is the impact location, D_{ij} are elements of the bending stiffness matrix \mathbf{D} , w is the out-of-plane displacement, r is the density, and h is the thickness of the laminate.

The assumed modes method, which is a Rayleigh-Ritz solution in terms of energy with assumed shape functions that satisfy the geometric boundary conditions, is then applied to equation (1). By choosing shape functions $f(x,y)$ to satisfy boundary conditions, the approximation of the displacement w by N_m terms of shape functions yields

$$w(x, y, t) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N_m} \bar{w}_i(t) f_i(x, y) \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the equation of motion can be written as follows

$$\mathbf{M} \frac{d^2 \bar{\mathbf{w}}}{dt^2} + \mathbf{K} \bar{\mathbf{w}} = \mathbf{L} f(t) \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{w}}$ is the generalized displacement vector and $\bar{\mathbf{w}} = [\bar{w}_1 \ \bar{w}_2 \ \dots \ \bar{w}_{N_m}]^T$; \mathbf{L} , \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{K} are the generalized force location, mass and stiffness matrices, respectively.

Defining the state vector $\mathbf{z} = [\bar{\mathbf{w}} \ \dot{\bar{\mathbf{w}}}]^T$, equation (3) can be formulated in the state space form

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{B} f(t) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{z} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{L} \end{bmatrix}$, and \mathbf{C} is the output matrix and \mathbf{y} is the output response.

Assuming zero order hold for the input, the system is converted from the continuous form to the discrete form, namely

$$\mathbf{z}(n+1) = \mathbf{\Phi} \mathbf{z}(n) + \mathbf{\Gamma} f(n) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(n) = \mathbf{Cz}(n) \quad (7)$$

where $\Phi = \exp(\mathbf{A}T_s)$, $\Gamma = \int_0^{T_s} \exp(\mathbf{A}t)dt\mathbf{B}$, T_s is the discrete sampling time and n represents the sampling points at time $t_n = nT_s$ ($n = 0, 1, \dots, N_s$) in which N_s is the total number of sampling points. Provided that the system has zero initial conditions, the substitution of equation (6) into equation (7) to solve for $\mathbf{y}(n)$ yields

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{F} \quad (8)$$

with

$$\mathbf{Y} = \{\mathbf{y}(1); \mathbf{y}(2); \dots; \mathbf{y}(N_s - 1); \mathbf{y}(N_s)\} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{F} = \{f(0); f(1); f(2); \dots; f(N_s - 2); f(N_s - 1)\} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}\Gamma & 0 & 0 & \dots & \mathbf{L} & 0 \\ \mathbf{C}\Phi\Gamma & \mathbf{C}\Gamma & 0 & \dots & \mathbf{L} & 0 \\ \mathbf{C}\Phi^2\Gamma & \mathbf{C}\Phi\Gamma & \mathbf{C}\Gamma & \dots & \mathbf{L} & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{M} & \dots & \mathbf{O} & \mathbf{M} \\ \mathbf{C}\Phi^{N_s-1}\Gamma & \mathbf{C}\Phi^{N_s-2}\Gamma & \mathbf{C}\Phi^{N_s-3}\Gamma & \dots & \mathbf{L} & \mathbf{C}\Gamma \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{Y} is the assembled measured system response vector (e.g. strain), \mathbf{F} is the assembled unknown impact force vector, \mathbf{H} is the lower block triangular Hankel matrix consisting of the system Markov parameters. From equation (8), when the impact location (x_{impact}, y_{impact}) is provided, the unknown impact force vector \mathbf{F} could be determined from the measurement vector \mathbf{Y} . Afterwards, we can reconstruct the impact force time history $f(t)$ from \mathbf{F} .

3 NON-NEGATIVE BAYESIAN REGULARIZATION FOR IMPACT IDENTIFICATION

In general, it is not straightforward to identify the impact force time history by a direct matrix inversion of equation (8), since the inverse problem may be ill-posed (e.g. \mathbf{H} is singular) when measurement noise and modeling error are present. To be consistent with the non-negative property, in this study, Bayesian regularization with non-negative constraints is employed to identify the impact force.

The basic idea is to encapsulate the unknown force vector \mathbf{F} into the posterior probability density function (PDF) $p(\mathbf{F}, t, a, b | \mathbf{Y})$ through hierarchical Bayesian modelling, given by

$$p(\mathbf{F}, t, a, b | \mathbf{Y}) \propto p(\mathbf{Y} | \mathbf{F}, t) p(\mathbf{F} | a, b) p(a) p(b) p(t) \quad (12)$$

where $p(\mathbf{Y} | \mathbf{F}, t)$ is the likelihood function and $p(\mathbf{F} | a, b)$ is the prior PDF of \mathbf{F} .

By assuming that the prediction error between the model outputs and the measurements follows normal distribution, the likelihood function can be expressed as

$$p(\mathbf{Y} | \mathbf{F}, t) \propto t^{N_s N_s / 2} \exp\left\{-\frac{t}{2} \|\mathbf{H}\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{Y}\|^2\right\} \quad (13)$$

where t is the precision (the reciprocal of variance) of the prediction error due to measurement noise and modeling error, $\|\mathbf{g}\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm.

For the unknown impact force vector \mathbf{F} , to ensure the non-negativity of its components f_n (here for the sake of concise, $f(n)$ is written as f_n), the prior PDF of \mathbf{F} is defined as [11]

$$p(\mathbf{F} | a, b) = \begin{cases} \frac{2b^a}{\Gamma(a)} \prod_{n=1}^{N_s} (f_n)^{2a-1} \exp(-b \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} f_n^2) & f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{N_s} \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Conjugate prior PDFs are adopted for the hyperparameters t , a and b , which are modeled by the Gamma distribution, written as

$$p(t) = \frac{b_1^{a_1}}{\Gamma(a_1)} t^{a_1-1} \exp(-b_1 t) \quad t \geq 0 \quad (15)$$

$$p(a) = \frac{b_2^{a_2}}{\Gamma(a_2)} \frac{1}{2} \exp\left(-\frac{a}{2}\right) \quad a \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad (16)$$

$$p(b) = \frac{b_3^{a_3}}{\Gamma(a_3)} b^{a_3-1} \exp(-b_3 b) \quad b \geq 0 \quad (17)$$

where $\{a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, a_3, b_3\}$ are hyperparameters of the conjugate prior PDFs.

The substitution of equations (13)-(17) into equation (12) yields

$$p(\mathbf{F}, t, a, b | \mathbf{Y}) \propto \exp \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} a \ln b - N_s \ln \Gamma(a) + (2a - 1) \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} \ln f_n - b \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} f_n^2 - \frac{t}{2} \|\mathbf{H}\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{Y}\|^2 + (N_s N_o / 2 + a_1 - 1) \ln t - b_1 t - (a_2 - 1) \ln(a - 1/2) - b_2 a + (a_3 - 1) \ln b - b_3 b \right\} \quad (18)$$

The Bayesian inference approach maximizes the posterior PDF in equation (18) so as to obtain a *maximum a posteriori* (MAP) estimate of the parameter set, which is equivalent to solve the four optimality equations, expressed as [11]

$$(t \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H} + 2b \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{F} - a \begin{bmatrix} 1/f_1 \\ 1/f_2 \\ \vdots \\ 1/f_{N_s} \end{bmatrix} - t \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{0} \quad (19)$$

$$- 2 \sum_{n=1}^{N_s} \ln f_n - N_s \ln b + N_s \frac{\Gamma'(a)}{\Gamma(a)} - \frac{(a_2 - 1)}{(a - 1/2)} + b_2 = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_s} f_n^2 - \frac{(N_s a + a_3 - 1)}{b} + b_3 = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{H}\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{Y}\|^2 - \frac{a}{t} + b_1 = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $a\phi = 2a - 1$, $a\dot{\phi} = (N_s N_o / 2 + a_1 - 1)$, $G\dot{\phi}(a)$ is the derivative of $G(a)$.

An alternating iterative algorithm is employed to obtain a convergent solution of $\{t, a, b\}$ and in the iterations a nonlinear Gauss-Seidel iterative algorithm is adopted to solve equation (19) to determine an optimal solution of \mathbf{F} . The details of the algorithm can be found in reference [11].

4 NUMERICAL STUDY

To demonstrate the effectiveness and performance of the proposed novel approach on impact load identification, numerical studies are conducted. Synthetic responses are generated as the reference measurements using a finite element model by ABAQUS. Zero-mean white noises are added to the synthetic data to simulate the measurement noise corruption. The numerical example considered in this study is a square composite plate with dimensions of 1000 mm \times 1000 mm. The composite plate consists of T300 graphite fibers and QY8911 epoxy matrix, with the layups of $[45/90/-45/0/0/45/0/0/-45/0]_s$. The thickness of each lamina is 0.125 mm, and the material properties of T300/QY8911 lamina are presented in Table 1. The laminate is modeled by 1600 reduced integration general purpose shell elements, S4R, with a uniform element size of 25 mm \times 25 mm. All of the four edges of the plate are clamped. A set of four sensors, designated as S1, S2, S3 and S4, are employed to measure the strain responses under the impact. The coordinates of S1, S2, S3 and S4 are (250, 250) mm, (750, 250) mm, (750, 750) mm and (250, 750) mm, respectively.

Table 1 Material properties of T300/QY8911 lamina

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ρ (kg/m ³)
135	8.8	4.47	0.3	1560

In the numerical studies, a typical half-sine impact force history as shown in Figure 1(a) is adopted. In the dynamic analysis, the sampling frequency is set as 25 kHz corresponding to a sampling interval of 0.04 ms. Figure 1(b) shows a comparison of the impact responses obtained by the finite element model and the state-space model (labelled as 'FE' and 'SS' for short, respectively), when the impact force acts on location (350, 400) mm. The strain invariant on the upper surface of the composite plate, which can be conveniently measured by bi-axial strain gauge or piezoelectric wafer, is used as the dynamic response. It can be seen that the outputs of the state-space model agree quite well with the finite element model results, demonstrating the modeling approach using the Rayleigh-Ritz type assumed modes method is satisfactory.

Figure 2 Impact force and dynamic responses: (a) impact force (b) comparison of responses

After the Rayleigh-Ritz type state-space model is validated, synthetic responses generated by ABAQUS and contaminated by Gaussian noise are fed to the non-negative Bayesian regularization method to iteratively reconstruct the impact force time history. In this study, impact localization is not

considered and the impact location is assumed as known beforehand. Gaussian noise with two noise levels, i.e., signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 20 dB and 10 dB, is added to the clean responses. Figure 3(a) shows the identified impact force when the SNR is 20 dB. The true impact force time history is also given for comparison purpose. It can be seen that the reconstructed impact force is in a good agreement with the true impact force despite the oscillation discrepancy exists. In general, the reconstructed shape, duration and peak value of the impact force well match those of the true impact load time history. In contrary to traditional Tikhonov regularization and Bayesian regularization without considering non-negative constraints, all the components of the identified impact force vector are non-negative, which is consistent with the physical property of true impact force. Figure 3(b) shows comparisons between the measured impact responses and the predicted responses. A good agreement can be observed between the measured and the predicted responses. Figure 4(a) and (b) show the identified impact force time history as well as the predicted responses when the SNR is increased to be 10dB. Again, it can be seen that the identified impact force and the predicted responses match the true one quite well, though measurement noise is increased significantly.

Figure 2 Force identified results when SNR=20dB (a) reconstructed force (b) predicted responses

Figure 3 Force identified results when SNR=10dB (a) reconstructed force (b) predicted responses

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel approach for simultaneously identifying the impact location and reconstructing the impact force time history acting on a composite structure through dynamic measurements. The proposed algorithm employs Bayesian regularization with non-negative constraints to solve the ill-posed impact force identification problem, while considering the physical property of impact force. The performance of the proposed approach is validated by numerical studies

based on a composite plate. The results show that the proposed approach can accurately identify the impact location and successfully reconstructs the impact force time histories. The shape, duration and peak of the reconstructed forces agree with those of the true force quite well. The overall satisfactory performance of the proposed algorithm illustrates its potential to be applied in impact load identification for composite structures in real applications.

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